

Organophosphate-Based Chemicals, Axonal Transport, and Cognitive Dysfunction

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ABBREVIATIONS

OP Organophosphates

ABSTRACT

Organophosphates (OPs) are toxic chemicals that are almost ubiquitous in our environment and they pose a significant health risk to millions of people worldwide. While the acute toxicity of OPs has been studied extensively, the effects of repeated exposures to levels of OPs not associated with acute toxicity, especially on cognitive function are poorly understood. Using animal models and *in vitro* methods we have established that repeated (subacute) exposures to some OPs can lead to protracted deficits in several domains of cognition, and that impairment in axonal transport may represent a potential underlying mechanism of these adverse effects.

INTRODUCTION

Organophosphates (OPs) are found in hundreds of useful products including pesticides, defoliants, fire retardants, industrial solvents, lubricants, plasticizers, and fuel additives.¹ Unfortunately, many OPs are highly toxic and deleterious health effects of OPs in humans have been documented.^{2,3} In the case of acute poisoning, the mechanism of both the acute symptoms of OP toxicity and the long-term neurological consequences of acute toxicity is well established. Specifically, inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) by the OP leads to marked

elevations in synaptic acetylcholine levels which in turn lead to excessive stimulation of both muscarinic and nicotinic acetylcholine receptors.^{4,5} Depending on the exposure level, some of the acute effects of OPs including excessive secretions, cardiorespiratory depression, and seizures can be life threatening. These acute effects of OP exposure can also lead to a variety of long-term neurological and psychiatric consequences in survivors. In contrast to acute OP poisoning, the long-term consequences of repeated exposures to levels of OPs below the threshold for acute “cholinergic” toxicity are less clear and controversial. This type of exposure is relatively common in agricultural workers and pesticide sprayers and it has been associated with persistent alterations in psychomotor speed, executive function, visuospatial ability, working and visual memory.⁶ Lower level, repeated exposures to OPs have also been associated with a variety with adverse symptoms in other contexts. For example, low-level exposures to OP-based insecticides (e.g., chlorpyrifos, dichlorvos) as well as nerve agent-OPs (sarin and cyclosarin) following the destruction of an Iraqi munitions storage complex at Khamisiyah, Iraq, in March 1991 have been implicated in the etiology of Gulf War illness (GWI), which affects up to one-fourth of the veterans from the first gulf war. GWI is characterized by a complex set of symptoms including unexplained fatigue, respiratory difficulties, musculoskeletal pain, gastrointestinal distress, skin rashes, headaches, and a variety of neurological and neuropsychiatric problems including cognitive impairment.⁷ In addition, repeated exposures to the OP, tri-cresyl phosphate (TCP), used as an anti-wear additive to jet engine oil, has been implicated in “aerotoxic syndrome” a term used to describe acute and persistent symptoms reported by aircrew following exposures to fumes in aircraft cabins. Symptoms include ear/nose/throat irritation, skin conditions, nausea and vomiting, respiratory problems, headaches, weakness and fatigue, nerve pain, tremors, and cognitive.^{8,9}

Need for prospective studies

It is important to note that there are a number of confounding factors that can limit the interpretations of the human studies described above, particularly when

attempts are made to make causal connections between illness symptoms and specific underlying biological mechanisms. Most of the human literature on OP exposures is based on retrospective investigations, case reports, and epidemiology and in each of the conditions, the study subjects were likely exposed to multiple substances as well as additional environmental insults or conditions (e.g., heat, stress, smoke, high altitude). Other factors that could confound the interpretations of the aforementioned studies include the inability to establish clear dose-effect relationships and the length of the periods of exposure to particular OPs. Therefore, a critical need exists for prospective studies (that can only be conducted ethically in non-human model systems) to determine what neurobiological consequences can indeed be linked directly to repeated exposures to particular OPs and when adverse effects can be linked, to establish dose-effect and exposure-time relationships and well as the underlying biological mechanisms of the adverse effects.

Summary of studies conducted in our laboratory

Based on the information provided above, one major goal of our laboratory is to prospectively investigate (in model systems) the effects of repeated exposures to OPs at doses/concentrations not associated with acute toxicity. Our behavioral results in rodents to date indicate that this type of exposure can result in a variety of cognition-related deficits that have been reported in humans including impairments in spatial learning and memory, sustained attention, and cognitive flexibility.¹⁰⁻¹⁵ We have also investigated potential mechanisms of the cognitive symptoms described above and have observed OP-related alterations in neurotrophin receptors and cholinergic proteins in brain regions that are important to cognitive function (e.g., cortex, hippocampus).^{11,13} Moreover, we have observed OP-related decreases in axonal transport in several studies, observations that may explain the alterations neurotrophin receptors, cholinergic proteins, and cognitive impairments. For example, we have observed decreases in the transport of vesicles in sciatic nerves ex vivo,¹¹ impairments in the movement of mitochondria and membrane bound organelles (MBOs) in axons in primary neuronal

culture,¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and deficits in the transport of a manganese (Mn^{2+})-based contrast agent in the optic nerve pathway of living rats using a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) method.¹⁹ Given the fundamental importance of axonal transport to neuronal health and function, these observations led us to hypothesize that OP-related deficits in axonal transport may contribute to many of the long-term neurological and psychiatric effects that have been attributed to OPs.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of our prospective animal experiments to date with the insecticide OP, chlorpyrifos (CPF) and the nerve agent, diisopropylfluorophosphate (DFP), have established that repeated exposures to OPs to levels that are below the threshold for acute toxicity can lead to protracted deficits in spatial learning, memory, and sustained attention. Moreover, our experiments suggest that impairments in axonal transport may represent a potential underlying mechanism of these adverse effects of OPs. In future studies, our laboratory will further investigate the mechanism of the OP-related impairments in axonal transport to identify therapeutic targets so that more effective treatment strategies can be developed for OP-related illnesses.

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